

SAFE PLN

Memorandum of Understanding

Executive summary

The libraries of Gent Universiteit, Lund Universitet, Université Catholique de Louvain, Universität Bielefeld, Université de Genève, Université de Montréal, and Université libre de Bruxelles are joining efforts to maintain a long-term preservation solution for open-access digital collections of publications and research data.

This solution, named SAFE PLN (SAFE Archiving Federation Private LOCKSS Network) is an international distributed preservation network based on the open-source preservation software LOCKSS (Lots Of Copies Keep Stuff Safe) developed at Stanford University.

This document describes the multilateral agreement between parties implied in the project in terms of technical and organizational implementations.

SAFE PLN (SAFE Archiving Federation Private LOCKSS Network) is a robust digital distributed preservation network based on the LOCKSS technology developed by Stanford University.

LOCKSS technology allowed CLOCKSS to earn the *highest score ever* received by an organization for the category “Technologies, Technical Infrastructure, and Security” after an 8-months long audit performed by independent experts of the Center for Research Libraries (CRL) in the context of its certification as a trustworthy digital repository for e-journal content [CRL14].

However, solely implementing a LOCKSS-based network is not a sufficient condition to guarantee the creation of a robust digital preservation repository. LOCKSS is indeed a versatile technology and the choices of the infrastructure configuration, software settings and organizational structure are key to ensure that archives will be safe in the long-term.

SAFE PLN aims at complying with *all required features of an efficient and robust bit-level preservation solution* tailored for the archiving of the original resources owned by partner institutions (mainly original dissertations, articles and datasets).

The SAFE PLN collaboration started in 2013 and amply proved its viability over the last ten years.

This Memorandum of Understandings (MoU) describes the multilateral agreement between SAFE PLN members on technical and operational implementations to guarantee the integrity, the security and the sustainability of the archives stored in the preservation network.

Section 1 formally identifies the institutions participating in the project.
Section 2 specifies the terms of collaboration, rights and responsibilities.
Section 3 describes the infrastructure of SAFE PLN.
Section 4 defines SAFE PLN archive model.
Section 5 presents SAFE PLN organization.
Section 6 contains signature of members
Appendix details how SAFE PLN is deploying efforts to mitigate threats that might affect the integrity of the archived content.

1. Participating institutions

Seven institutions started the operation and the development of the SAFE PLN preservation network:

Ghent University (UGent), public institution with legal personality, having its administrative offices in Belgium, B-9000 Gent, Sint-Pietersnieuwstraat 25 and duly represented by [name of the person], [position];

Lunds Universitet (LU), public institution with legal personality, having its administrative offices in Sweden, SE-223 50 Lund, Paradisgatan 2 and represented [name of the person], [position];

Universität Bielefeld (Uni-Bielefeld), public institution with legal personality, having its administrative offices in Germany, 33615 Bielefeld, Universitätsstraße 25, and duly represented [name of the person], [position];

Université Catholique de Louvain (UCLouvain), public institution with legal personality, having its administrative offices in Belgium, B-1348 Louvain-la-Neuve, Place de l'Université 1, and duly represented [name of the person], [position];

Université de Genève (UNIGE), public institution with legal personality, having its administrative offices in Switzerland, CH-1211 Genève 4, Rue du Général-Dufour 24, and represented [name of the person], [position];

Université de Montréal (UdeM), public institution with legal personality, having its administrative offices in Canada, Québec, Montréal, 2900, boul. Édouard-Montpetit and represented [name of the person], [position];

Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB), public institution with legal personality, having its administrative offices in Belgium, B-1050 Bruxelles, Avenue Franklin Roosevelt 50 - CP180 and duly represented [name of the person], [position].

The seven members prepared and signed the present MoU.

2. Terms of collaboration

Each member agrees to take part in the project for an initial period of three years automatically renewable for successive periods of three years, unless terminated by other parties. Should a member wish to leave SAFE PLN, a one year prior-notice will be issued before quitting the project.

The introduction of a new partner in the project must be accepted by all parties representative and the new partner will have to sign an addendum to this MoU.

The present MoU may only be amended by mutual written agreement signed by the authorized representatives of all Parties. Each Party shall give full consideration to any proposal for an amendment made by any other Party.

The Parties are not creating a legal partnership, joint venture or other joint enterprise and this collaboration is not to be understood as such. Each Party is completely independent of the other but the Parties are collaborating together in defined ways to achieve mutual goals. This MoU represents a nonexclusive collaboration between the Parties, and nothing contained in this MoU precludes either Party from pursuing other same or similar opportunities, entering into relationships regarding the same or similar subject matter described in this MOU, or participating in other similar relationships with third parties, including but not limited to competitors of the other Party.

SAFE PLN Members Rights

- SAFE PLN members are ensured of the distribution of the archived content in seven copies across the preservation nodes on the SAFE PLN infrastructure (providing all nodes are operational).
- SAFE PLN members can ingest new archived content in the preservation network, providing that required storage capacity for their whole archived content does not exceed the maximum authorized storage capacity per institution (this storage capacity is updated once a year by means of a unanimous decision of SAFE PLN managers).
- SAFE PLN members have the ability to monitor the status of their archived content in the network, including the crawling status and integrity reports.
- SAFE PLN members can participate to annual SAFE PLN meetings and conference calls.

SAFE PLN Members Responsibilities

- SAFE PLN members are responsible for the set-up and the maintenance of their preservation node. In case of a node failure, the institution will deploy best efforts to make the node available again within the shortest possible delay.
- SAFE PLN members authorize other members to use their copy for the sake of data integrity monitoring and repair and to guarantee access to their preservation node through specific LOCKSS protocol.
- SAFE PLN members provide access to the LOCKSS daemon status information to other members.
- each SAFE PLN member designates one technical administrator and one manager and must inform other members of any change via the general mailing list.

- a membership subscription to the LOCKSS Alliance is not required but it is strongly encouraged to support the future development of the LOCKSS daemon.
- SAFE PLN members cannot ingest content that is outside the scope of the collaboration (see Section 4) without approval of the other members.

3. SAFE PLN general description

Fundamentals

SAFE PLN is based on five principles:

1. SAFE PLN is an international federation, not limited to a specific region, country or organization.
2. SAFE PLN is managed by a light organizational structure based on a memorandum of understanding.
3. each SAFE PLN partner keeps technical control and visibility on their archived collections.
4. each SAFE PLN partner can monitor its preserved content over the network.
5. budgets of SAFE PLN partners remain fully independent.

SAFE PLN Infrastructure

SAFE PLN is currently composed of 7 preservation nodes distributed amongst institutions as follows:

- 1 preservation node at LU
- 1 preservation node at UCLouvain
- 1 preservation node at UdeM
- 1 preservation node at UGent
- 1 preservation node at Uni-Bielefeld
- 1 preservation node at UNIGE
- 1 preservation node at ULB (+ 2 test nodes)

In addition to the seven core nodes dedicated to preservation, two auxiliary servers complete the network: an administrative server and a monitoring server currently hosted and administered at ULB.

Preservation nodes

SAFE PLN preservation nodes are servers dedicated to run exclusively the LOCKSS daemon. For obvious security reasons, no other network service may run on the server with the exception of ssh, ntp and monitoring services. It is recommended that a backup solution is enabled on the file system dedicated to archive content to enable fast and seamless hard disk change in case of a disk failure to avoid the lengthy process of rebuilding the entire box content from scratch.

All machines in the network are referred to as their IP address and not hostnames.
All communications between caches and to the administration interface are secured.

Administrative server

The administrative server contains SAFE LOCKSS network configuration parameters, the description of the archived content (title database) and the description of the method to collect the content (plugins).

The technical administrator from each member institution has read access to the administrative server and can ask the administrative server administrators to commit and update the configuration files related to their own collections (e.g. to update the title database configuration when new content needs to be injected in the network). Any parameter change is thus logged and exposed to every node.

Should the main administrative server be unavailable for a period of time exceeding a week, a backup server will be activated. Should the admin server be attacked, the effect on the preservation network itself would be limited as the LOCKSS daemon performs boundary checks of the parameters to avoid problems. Any form of attack can in no way destroy the archived content stored in the preservation nodes.

AU publishers and archive ingest process in SAFE

The ingest process is a manual process to ensure that the content to be archived has been curated before being submitted in the network.

At the beginning of the year, each SAFE member prepares a new archive collection (called an Archival Unit (AU)) on their own staging server called an AU publisher to archive their collections of the previous year:

- Each member starts by collecting the objects to be archived from their institutional repository that were created or have been modified during the previous year.
- Objects are packaged together with their descriptive, administrative, and technical metadata in a bag-it zip file.
- Members then create manifest pages for their collections on their staging server pointing to the bags.
- A new entry is then created manually in the title database for each new AU.
- Crawling of the new AUs is tested on one of our test LOCKSS box.
- If the crawling is successful, an email is sent asking members to add the newly available AU to their LOCKSS boxes.
- Finally, when an AU has been collected in all boxes and the quorum for this AU is reached in each box (observable with the dashboard), we set the flag “pub down” to true in the title database so that the boxes stop crawling the AUs from the staging server.
- The AU can then be deleted from the staging server.

Dashboard and Monitoring server

All nodes in the network (the boxes themselves, the administrative server and the AU publishers) are constantly monitored by a dedicated server currently hosted at ULB.

The server collects the logs and performance metrics from all the machines in the SAFE infrastructure as well as the status data and logs from all LOCKSS daemon.

Automatic alerts are sent to SAFE PLN members in case of a problem/warning to a dedicated mailing list.

Access to the dashboard server is provided to all technical and organizational members of the network.

Public status data is made available via the website www.safepln.org (for security reasons, it is a daily updated screenshot of the dashboard).

4. SAFE PLN archive scope

SAFE PLN is a dark archive implemented as a private network initially targeting open access collections harvested from SAFE PLN members' institutional repositories (mainly original dissertations, scientific articles and research datasets). In the future, the scope of the archive may be extended to delayed-access publications (open-access after an embargo period) or similar collections.

The content of the nodes cannot be transmitted to third-parties not involved in the project without the prior express agreement of the competent authority.

Each party shall acknowledge that data stored in the SAFE PLN cannot be deleted or modified by any other party.

5. SAFE PLN Organization

A robust preservation solution needs to be based on independent administration of their preservation nodes. The nodes should be hosted in various institutions in different political and organizational contexts.

The public institutions participating in SAFE PLN are subsidized by various and mostly independent funding sources and are subject to different legal jurisdictions.

SAFE PLN is based on a light organization structure. The LOCKSS technology is perfectly adapted to this kind of structure as only a small amount of material and human resources needs to be shared. Infrastructure budgets can remain independent as the agreement mainly consists in sharing resources.

SAFE PLN members shall endeavor to settle their disputes amicably.

Any dispute, controversy or claim arising under, out of or relating to this collaboration, including, without limitation, its formation, validity, binding effect, interpretation, performance, breach or termination, as well as non-contractual claims, shall be submitted to mediation for example in accordance with the [WIPO Mediation Rules](#) or other relevant mediation rules.

The place of mediation shall be Brussels unless otherwise agreed upon. The language to be used in the mediation shall be English unless otherwise agreed upon.

If, and to the extent that, any such dispute, controversy or claim has not been settled pursuant to the mediation within 60 calendar days of the commencement of the mediation, the courts of Brussels shall have exclusive jurisdiction.

Nothing in this Consortium Agreement shall limit the Parties' right to seek injunctive relief in any applicable competent court.

SAFE-PLN members participate to a face-to-face or online meeting once a year, typically in the context of a popular digital library conference. Virtual meetings are also planned when necessary.

Various mailing distribution lists allow concerned members to communicate:

- General topics: [email]
- Technical topics: [email]
- Public relation: [email]

All organizational and technical documents related to SAFE PLN will be preserved in the network.

Besides official representatives named in section 1, Table 1 lists the current responsible persons for SAFE-PLN operations.

For each institution, a manager and a technical administrator are designated. Managers are responsible for SAFE PLN strategical decisions. Technical administrators are responsible for SAFE PLN preservation nodes operations and maintenance.

Institution	Technical Administrator	Manager
Uni-Bielefeld	[name of the person] [email]	[name of the person] [email]
UGent	Id	Id
UNIGE	Id	Id
LU	Id	Id
UCLouvain	Id	Id
UdeM	Id	Id
ULB	Id	Id

Table 1: SAFE-PLN staff members (as of [date])

6. Signatures

Institution	Name	Signature
UGent	[name of the person] [email]	Date:
Uni-Bielefeld	Id	Date:
UCLouvain	Id	Date:
UNIGE	Id	Date:
UdeM	Id	Date:
ULB	Id	Date:
LU	Id	Date:

Appendix: Preservation risks mitigation

This section describes how SAFE PLN is deploying efforts to mitigate threats which might affect our archives.

Geo-replication

Risk

A natural hazard could simultaneously disable or destroy several preservation nodes, dangerously reducing the set of operational nodes to the point where the archived content integrity would be compromised.

Mitigation measures

SAFE PLN is an international network composed of a minimum of seven nodes disseminated across the world. Each of the nodes constituting the network contains a complete copy of the archived content. The complete loss of a preservation node caused by e.g. natural disaster would not compromise the network as long as the node repair or replacement is performed shortly.

A common rule of thumb is that preservation nodes should be located at a minimum of 100 km apart from each other in safe places, on different power grids to mitigate the impact of various kind of hazards (fires, flooding, hurricane, tornado, earthquake, CMEs, power failures).

Three nodes in the network are situated in Belgium at shorter distance but the very low probability of a natural disaster affecting simultaneously those sites counterbalances their relative proximity.

Each member can thus track modification realized in the network.

Independent technical management

Risk

An erroneous or deliberate act performed by a SAFE PLN technical administrator could simultaneously disable, compromise or destroy all preservation nodes content.

Mitigation measures

SAFE PLN advocates a fully independent management of the nodes technical administration. Each institution hosting a box has the required technical know-how and is responsible for the technical management of the hardware and the software configuration of its machine.

Each participating institution designate one technical administrator and a backup.

A technical administration error on one SAFE PLN box would thus only affect at most one individual box and would not compromise the network integrity.

An error at the administration server level would affect the entire network but in no way could it results in a loss or damage to the archived content as property values outside an acceptable range are automatically rejected by LOCKSS daemon.

Moreover, all operator access is logged and web interface actions cause alerts.

Cost control

Risk

The budgets of SAFE PLN members could be restricted to the point where they could not afford investing in their preservation solution to ensure in-time replacement of equipment and disk repair, gradually exposing the hardware to increasing risk of failure.

Mitigation measures

SAFE PLN requires a small investment both in terms of hardware and maintenance staff.

The expenses mainly consist in buying hardware and ensuring maintenance of the preservation node mid-range hardware and travel costs for participating to annual meetings. The staff cost is limited as the maintenance only requires an hour of work/month once the solution is set-up.

Budgets remain completely independent. Partners agree to share resources with the others.

External attacks

Risk

Preservation nodes are connected to the internet and thus exposed to external attacks. If an attacker grants access to preservation nodes through its web UI or SSH, it could compromise or destroy archived content.

Mitigation measures

The administrative access on SAFE PLN boxes is limited to the staff of the hosting institution. All communication between the LOCKSS box and to the LOCKSS box are secured with SSL. Administrative access is logged and administrative actions cause alerts.

- access requires https
- administrative access is logged
- administrative actions are logged and create alerts

SSH access to the preservation node is restricted by firewall settings to only local or VPN access.

Regular security update of the OS and of the lockss daemon.

By default, LOCKSS proxy feature is disabled in SAFE PLN as archived content is not meant to be accessible from outside.

Hardware obsolescence and failure

Risk

Hardware can and will fail. Hard disks are typically the most vulnerable piece of hardware. The risk of simultaneous media failures or exposure to bugs in the network increases when the same hardware is bought at the same time from the same provider.

Mitigation measures

The choice of hardware is left to the host institution to promote heterogeneity and thus mitigate the risk of simultaneous hardware failures.

The following minimum system specifications are required:

- Quad Core Intel Core i7 processor
- Rack-mountable server chassis
- 6 GB RAM
- 2 TB raw disk space
- RAID recommended (mirroring or striping+parity)
- CentOS 6.x (or RHEL6)
- OpenJDK 1.6
- physically secure, accessible only to authorized staff, climate controlled
- firewall set to block all unused ports
- min user accounts
- no root ssh login from a public interface
- regular security updates

The hardware status is constantly monitored through a dedicated server. If a problem occurs, an automatic alert is sent to all technical administrators.

The technical staff of the host institutions should replace the media shortly.

All parties will make a LOCKSS cache node available for the SAFE PLN grid with a capacity of 2 Terabytes of raw storage. All parties agree that the maximum raw storage capacity per institution in the SAFE PLN is currently set to 200GB. The storage capacity requirements will be adapted every year by mutual agreement.

Enabling RAID on the filesystem used by the LOCKSS cache for archive storage is recommended to ensure a better up-time and to avoid entirely recreating the node content in case of a single disk failure.

The hardware lifetime is typically estimated to 5 years. Hardware should be replaced following yearly updated specifications.

Following a complete loss of a node and/or at the express demand of a the owner institution, the archive can be retrieved from a SAFE PLN node configured as a proxy. The host institution delivering the copy needs to temporarily

Archive content integrity

Risk

Data stored on hard disks is prone to data corruption (bit-rot), bad sectors resulting of physical damage on part of the disk and complete disk failures. If not handled in time, the archived data could be corrupted or completely lost.

Mitigation measures

Data monitoring is performed automatically and regularly by the LOCKSS daemon. The operations of the LOCKSS daemon are described in [Maniatis14]. When an error is detected, it is automatically repaired by the LOCKSS daemon following the LCAP protocol.

Bad sectors are handled by disk controllers and monitored by SMART reports.

Whole disk failures are automatically reported by the monitoring server. Assuming RAID is enabled, the loss of one hard drive does not result in data loss.

More generally, all network components status are monitored by the monitoring server. Alerts are automatically sent to all SAFE PLN technical administrators. Best efforts are deployed by the technical staff to repair hardware within the shortest possible delay.

The following parameters are monitored by SAFE PLN monitoring server:

- current load
- current users
- ping
- ntp
- ssh
- swap usage
- number of processes
- zombie processes
- https
- memory usage
- disk usage
- SMART disk status
- LOCKSS daemon status

Long-Term Archive Format Readability

Risk

Although bits have been perfectly preserved by SAFE PLN, the content is not exploitable in the long term future.

Mitigation measures

SAFE PLN is a bit-level preservation network, it is thus file-format agnostic.

However, SAFE PLN members are free to deploy their own format-migration solution to mitigate the risk of file format obsolescence.

Archives preserved in LOCKSS are structured in Archival Units (AUs). An AU is the minimum archiving granularity for LOCKSS used to monitor and repair content. An AU is typically a collection of digital objects.

Archived digital objects are structured as Archival Information Package (AIP).

Although digital collections are diverse and are harvested from various types of environment, SAFE PLN promotes the interoperability and readability of archives for the long-term future.

Hence, SAFE PLN members use the same basic template structure for all AIPs:

archive-ugent-be-[UUID] : BagIt

The bag-info.txt contains basic bag and Dublin Core description:

```
Archive-Id: archive.ugent.be:A225795C-379D-11E1-AB8F-6E523B7C8C91
Bag-Size: 29.8 MB
Bagging-Date: 2012-01-05
DC-AccessRights: open
DC-Creator: Sample, John
DC-DateAccepted: 2012-01-05
DC-Description:Microprocessorgestuurde koördinatentafel.
DC-Identifier: rug01:000284609
DC-Identifier: BIB.GTH.004487
DC-Subject: gthes
DC-Title: RUG01-000284609
DC-Type: Text
Payload-Oxum: 31290210.3
```

The marc.xml file contains MARC21 bibliographic data and the mets.xml file describes the data streams contained in the data folder contained in the bag.

Archive Content Ingest

Risk

By design, each LOCKSS daemon is collecting content to archive from the repository at different moments in time to avoid communication errors. However, if the repository content is dynamic, this results in a potential discrepancy between versions collected by the different nodes in the network which are in consequence unable to compare and check their integrity.

Mitigation measures

Archival content is not harvested directly from the institutional repositories but from the Archival Unit Publishers of each institution on a yearly basis.

The AU publisher is a simple html web server exposing AIPs to archive and defining AU structures by the mean of manifest pages. It freezes the very dynamic content of the repository in time. AIPs are created for each required object.

Archival Units are structured by year and by collection.

This ensures:

- source independence from the various institutional repositories in the network
- coherence of the AU which is harvested by the LOCKSS daemon at different moments in time to reduce the risk of communications

Once the archives have been ingested in the network and full agreement is obtained, the AU is marked as preserved by the network.

SAFE PLN AU publishers share a common website structure:

[./lockss/manifest.html](#) (main manifest page for all collections)

[./lockss/openaccess/openaccess.html](#) (manifest page for the open-access collection)

[./lockss/openaccess/2009/index.html](#) (manifest page for the 2009 open-access collection)

Every page that needs to be collected by the PLN should mention:

```
<p>LOCKSS system
has permission to collect, preserve, and serve this Archival Unit.</p>
```

Once the content from the Archival Unit Publisher has been ingested by all SAFE PLN nodes and the integrity check is successful, the corresponding AUs are marked as “down” in the title database to force LOCKSS nodes to repair from the copies in the network and not from the original source.

Bibliography

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[Maniatis14] Petros Maniatis, Mema Roussopoulos, TJ Giuli, David S.H. Rosenthal, Mary Baker, and Yanto Muliadi. “LOCKSS: A Peer-to-Peer Digital Preservation System”, ACM Transactions on Computer Systems vol. 23, no. 1, February 2005, pp. 2-50. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/1047915.1047917> [accessed 2023/09/25]